

Spectrophotometric Studies of 8-(*p*-Tolylsulphona-mido)-Quinoline Metal Chelates in Some Water-Miscible Organic Solvents

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8-(*p*-Tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline has been found by us¹ to form insoluble chelates with many cations. In the present communication we have studied spectrophotometrically the chelates formed by Cu (II), Zn (II), Cd (II), Ni (II), Pb (II) and UO₂ (II) with 8-(*p*-tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline in two water-miscible organic solvent systems, dimethylformamide as one and a mixture of equal volumes of *n*-propyl alcohol and 1, 4-dioxane as the other with the hope that these reactions might be suitable for their volumetric estimation by the photometric titration technique.

Experimental and Discussion

Preliminary investigations were made in each of the two solvents to establish the correct wave length, pH range, concentrations of the reagent and metallic ions and other suitable conditions for complete reaction. A wave length of 420 m μ was found suitable for all copper determinations. A pH range of 5.0-7.0 was found to give a constant maximum absorbance at 420 m μ . Reagent concentration and mole ratio was determined by plotting the absorbances of solutions containing 0.04M copper and reagent in molar ratio 1 : 0.2 to 1 : 5 at 420 m μ . The results indicated the ratio of reagent to copper for constant maximum absorbance as 2 : 1. Lambert Beer's Law was obeyed in the concentration range of 0.2 ppm to 8 ppm of copper at 420 m μ . The nature of the titration curves for copper in dimethylformamide and in dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol was essentially the same.

The titration curves for Zn (II) were very similar to those for copper with these solvents. The equilibrium near the equivalence point is less favourable for zinc than for copper titrations. To obtain an end point comparable with copper it was necessary to work with zinc concentrations about 10 times those for copper.

From the location of the end point for the titrations and the amount of copper or zinc present, it was found that 8-(*p*-tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline was reacting with these metal ions in the ratio of 2 : 1.

Cadmium may be titrated spectrophotometrically in dimethylformamide but with less satisfactory results than copper or zinc. The end point at the 2 : 1 ratio of the reagent to cadmium could be reproduced to $\pm 1\%$. The continued rise of the titration curve past the end point, though at a lesser inclination is probably due to the further addition of the reagent to cadmium complex. In dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol the end point is not reproducible because of the slow precipitation of the cadmium salt, causing a turbid solution.

Photometric titrations of nickel did not indicate breaks in the curve suitable for analytical determinations. The slope of the curve at a molar ratio of two reagents to one nickel began to increase rather than decrease as in the case of copper and zinc. This may be taken as evidence of the reaction of the reagent with nickel at a molar ratio greater than 2 : 1. Approaching a 3 : 1 ratio the slope of the curve decreased but with considerable curvature.

Solutions of Pb (II) and UO₂ (II) in dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol could not give any detectable break in the curve at a 2 : 1 molar ratio of the reagent to cation. The system followed Beer's Law relationship until some what past a 1 : 1 ratio of the reagent to cation, when the slope increased and continued beyond the 2 : 1 equivalence point. From the consideration of the results with nickel and cadmium it is reasonable to conclude that a third molecule of the reagent was interfering with these cations.

The results indicated that photometric titrations in water miscible organic solvents, in general, are comparable in accuracy and sensitivity with titrations in water, but are not so versatile.

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Reference

1. R. C. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 207.

Potentiometric Assay of Micromole Quantities of Methylene-blue using Hexanitrate Ammonium Cerate (IV)*

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MORRAW¹ proposed an iodometric method for the determination of methylene blue and claimed that one molecule of methylene blue absorbs five atoms of iodine in the presence of acetic acid, while others^{2, 3, 4} claimed that one molecule of methylene blue absorbs 6 atoms of iodine in the presence of sodium acetate. But Holmes⁵ stated that the amount of iodine taken up by methylene blue is proportional to the concentration of excess iodine present. Ferrey⁶, proposed an indirect method for the determination of methylene blue by precipitating it with excess dichromate, the excess being estimated iodometrically. Suprun⁷ determined methylene-blue iodo chlorometrically in acid as well as in alkaline medium. Picric acid was used as a reagent for volumetric⁸ and gravimetric⁹ determination of methylene blue. Several other gravimetric determinations of

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methylene blue were studied using dichromate¹⁰, perchlorate¹¹ and tungstosilicic acid¹², as precipitants.

Ti³⁺ and Cr²⁺ are used as volumetric reagents in an inert atmosphere for the direct titration of methylene blue at higher temperatures. Chernavina¹³ determined methylene blue by directly titrating oxidimetrically with Chloramine-T at an elevated temperature.

A survey of literature reveals a few potentiometric methods¹⁴⁻²⁰, for the assay of methylene blue involving rigorous conditions such as maintenance of inert atmosphere, elevated temperature etc. So we have taken up the study of potentiometric assay of micromole quantities of methylene blue oxidimetrically using hexanitrate ammonium cerate (IV). The advantages of the present method over the other methods are (i) inert atmosphere is unnecessary, (ii) it can be carried out at room temperature, (iii) reproducible stoichiometry over a wide range of concentrations and (IV) a large potential jump at the equivalence point.

Experimental

Reagents :

0.1M hexanitrate ammonium cerate (IV) : It is prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of G. R. E. Merck sample of hexanitrate ammonium cerate (IV) in one litre of deionized water maintaining an overall acidity of 1M nitric acid. This solution is diluted wherever necessary.

0.02M Methylene blue : The percentage purity of G. R. E. Merck sample of methylene blue is determined volumetrically with titanium (III) chloride²¹. Then the requisite amount is dissolved in one litre of deionized water, maintaining an overall acidity of 0.2M nitric acid.

B. D. H. Analar nitric acid is used throughout the investigation.

Apparatus : The potentiometric assembly consisted of a "Kaycee potentiometer" and a Cambridge suspension galvanometer, a bright platinum rod as the indicator electrode, a saturated calomel reference electrode and a saturated ammonium nitrate salt bridge.

General procedure : A suitable volume of hexanitrate ammonium cerate (IV) was transferred into a 150 ml titration vessel and sufficient amount of 1:1 nitric acid is added so as to keep the normality with respect to nitric acid at 1M and then diluted to 50 ml. The resulting mixture was titrated potentiometrically with a 2×10^{-3} M methylene blue solution from a micro-burette. The potentials were noted five minutes after the addition of each aliquot of methylene blue and after ten minutes near the equivalence point. A typical plot of volume of methylene blue added versus the potential measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E) was obtained. The potential break at the equivalence

point is about 300-350 mv per 0.05 ml. of 2×10^{-3} M methylene blue. Some representative results are given in Table 1 showing that the ratio of moles of cerium(IV) consumed per mole of methylene blue is constant indicating that the methylene blue is always oxidised to the same single product.

TABLE 1

Micromoles of Cerium (IV) taken	Micromoles of Methylene blue consumed	(Moles of Ce(IV) per mole of methylene blue)
235.75	8.48	27.81
339.40	12.20	27.85
565.80	20.30	27.88
613.00	21.70	28.25
660.1	23.40	28.21
		Average : 28.00

Results and Discussion

Under the experimental conditions described above 28 moles of Ce (IV) are reduced per mole of methylene blue. Experiments showed that the variation of nitric acid concentration from 0.5-1.5M did not affect either the accuracy or the speed of the titration, while greater concentration of nitric acid resulted in the higher consumption of methylene blue. At higher acidities the mole ratio will be less. The rose red oxidation product formed is extractable only into nitrobenzene and nitromethane, the product formed may be polar in character. The nitrobenzene extract is subsequently stable for long periods and is exhibiting strong fluorescence on dilution with ethanol or acetone. Further investigation regarding this aspect is in progress. From the stoichiometry obtained, we believe that the oxidation may proceed according to the equation

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Reference

- H. O. MORRAW, *J. Assoc. Official Agr. Chem.*, 1923, 7, 20.
- GONZALO, GURMENDI and JUAN DE. D. GUEVARA, *Bol. Soc. Quim. Peru.*, 1938, 4, 283.
- T. SABLITSCHKA and W. ERDMANN, *Pharm. Acta. Helv.*, 1940, 15, 162.
- H. O. MORRAW, *J. Assoc. Official Agr. Chem.*, 1941, 24, 806.
- W. C. HOLMES, *J. Assoc. Official Agr. Chem.*, 1927, 10, 505.
- G. J. W. FERREY, *Chemist Druggist.*, 1943, 140, 126.
- P. P. SUPRUN, *Med. Prom. S.S.S.R.*, 1958, 12, 38.
- ADOLPH BOLLIGER, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales.*, 1934, 67, 240.
- M. FRANCOIS and Mlle. L. SEGUIN, *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1929, 10, 5.
- G. J. W. FERREY, *Quart. J. Pharm.*, 1943, 16, 208.
- F. A. MAURINA and NEULON DEAHL, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1943, 32, 301.
- V. MARES and Z. STERSKAL, *Cesk. Farm.*, 1962, 11, 354.

13. E. KNETCH and E. HIBBERT, "New Reduction Methods in Volumetric Analysis", 2nd Ed. Longmans Green & Co. New York, 1925, p. 101.
14. J. P. TANDON and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 158, 189.
15. M. S. CHERNAVINA, *Trudy Sverdlovsk. Seiskokhoz Inst.*, 1960, 7, 363.
16. G. F. DAVIDSON, *Shirley Inst. Mem.*, 1947, 21, 29.
17. E. RUZICKA and M. KOTUCEK, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 180, 429.
18. E. RUZICKA, *Monatsh.*, 1962, 93, 1262.
19. A. A. PODOLENKO, *Izv. Akad. Nauk Moldavi, S.S.R.*, 1963, 9, 63.
20. V. RUKMINI, Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, (India) 1964.

Polarographic Studies on the Reaction Between Manganese Sulphate and Sodium Mandelate

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It has been found that mandelic acid forms 1:1 chelates with number of metals¹⁻⁴ due to liberation of hydroxy as well as carboxylic protons of mandelic acid.

Polarographic studies of manganese (II) complexes with some ligands have been done⁵⁻⁶. Studies on Mn(II)-mandelate complex are reported here.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of Analar quality and the solutions were prepared by using double distilled water. The polarograms were recorded on Tinsley pen recording polarograph. The pH values of each set was determined by Philips pH meter. All the operations were done at room temperature.

The experimental solutions were made keeping potassium chloride, manganese sulphate and gelatin concentrations constant at 1M, 0.00125M and 0.001% respectively and the ligand (sodium-mandelate) concentration was varied up to 0.01125 M.

The polarograms of these samples were recorded after keeping the sets of solutions for 24 hr. and deoxygenating each set by passing purified hydrogen.

The half-wave potential $E_{1/2}$ of each polarogram was determined⁷, and then the change in half-wave potential $\Delta E_{1/2}$ with change in ligand concentration was plotted against $\Delta \log C_x$ (logarithm of change in ligand concentration). The number of ligand ions (P) that are co-ordinated with one metal ion was calculated using the following relation⁸.

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta \log C_x} = -0.0591 \frac{P}{n}$$

and then the dissociation constant⁹ of the complex species by the following relation

$$(E_{1/2})_0 - (E_{1/2})_a = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log K_c - \frac{0.0591}{n} p \log C_x$$

The reversibility of the electrode reaction was verified by plotting $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ against the corresponding potential

E where i_d = diffusion current and i = current at any applied potential E.

The plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ Vs $\Delta \log C_x$ for experimental data gives a straight line, the value of p was calculated and was found to be equal to one, indicating the formation of a 1:1 Mn(II)-mandelate complex. The value of the formation constant, K, is 1×10^4 (30° and $\mu = 1.0055$ to 1.055).

References

1. VERMA and MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 35, 381.
2. KUMINES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 376.
3. HAHN and JOSEPH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1208.
4. KAPOOR and MEHROTRA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 3561.
5. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GOUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 436.
6. KABIRUDDIN, A. AZIZ and BEG., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 481.
7. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishing Inc., New York, 1955, p. 62.
8. I. MEITES, *Ibid.*, 1955, p. 116.
9. L. MEITES, *Ibid.*, 1955, p. 115.

Enthalpimetric Studies of Some Beryllium Complexes*

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CALORIMETRY provides a means for the direct measurement of enthalpy changes involved in complex forming reactions. Heat of reaction data for many metal ligand systems have been obtained from $\ln K$ vs $1/T$ plots (using sometimes only two temperatures). These are often of questionable validity since variations of $\ln K$ with temperature, in the intervals normally employed, are of the same order of magnitude as the uncertainties in the measurement of $\ln K$. Since, ΔH and not ΔG is a true measure of the metal ligand bond strength, the availability of reliable enthalpy values would lead to a better understanding of the factors affecting the strength of these bonds. The present paper describes the calorimetric measurement of enthalpy changes during the complexation of Be^{2+} with oxalate and malonate ions.

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